

Surgically Induced Astigmatism with Supero-Temporal Anti Smile (Frown) Incision in Small Incision Cataract Surgery a Hospital Based Study***Mallikarjun Raju P¹, K. Srinija², V. Lilly Joy³**¹Assistant Professor of Ophthalmology, Government Medical College, Eluru, Andhra Pradesh²Senior Resident, Government Medical College, Eluru, Andhra Pradesh³Senior Resident, Government Medical College, Eluru, Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Surgically induced astigmatism (SIA) is often the cause for poor recovery following Small Incision Cataract Surgery (SICS). The present study is an observational study assessing the incidence of surgically induced astigmatism with Supero-Temporal Anti Smile (Frown) incision in small incision cataract surgery.**Materials and Methods:** 100 individuals with significant visual loss due to cataract were included in the study and all have undergone Small Incision Cataract Surgery (SICS) through supero-temporal incision with Anti Smile (Frown) and were followed up for One month for surgically induced astigmatism.**Results:** There was a low incidence of surgically induced astigmatism of 7% and mean value of astigmatism of 1.107Diopters.**Conclusion:** Supero-temporal Anti Smile (Frown) incision with small incision cataract surgery gives a low incidence of surgically induced astigmatism and is highly suitable for beginners who learn SICS superiorly with assistance of Superior Rectus, as the approach to the Supero-Temporal is quite easy and for ALL SICS practitioners in rural centres where phacoemulsification is not feasible.**Keywords:** Surgically induced astigmatism, Small Incision Cataract Surgery, Supero temporal Anti Smile (Frown) Incision.

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Introduction

Cataract is considered as the most common cause for correctable visual loss in India. [1] According to the National Rapid Assessment of Blindness Survey (2015-2019) carried out by NPCB&VI across 31 districts of the country cataract was found to be a major cause of visual impairment in India accounting for 66.2% of blindness, 80.7% of severe visual impairment and 70.2% of moderate visual impairment. [2] Chatterjee et al observed that 82% of Indians in the age of 75 to 83 have significant visual impairment due to cataract or aphakia. [3] Astigmatism is one of the major contributors for suboptimal recovery of vision post-operatively following cataract surgery. [4] Although there are varied views on the causes of astigmatism following cataract surgery most of them agree up on the incision size and location. Evidence suggested that the more peripheral the incision, the lesser is the effect on the astigmatism. [5] Several studies have correlated the size of the incision with the colour and hardness of the nucleus of the lens [6,7,8] required larger incision for mature and hyper-mature cataract. In dense cataracts a superior and larger incision leads to higher incidence of surgically induced astigmatism.

Phacoemulsification has been widely used for cataract extraction world over. However the procedure would not be feasible in peripheral centres due to need for specialized equipment and cost. Small Incision Cataract Surgery (SICS) has been performed as an alternative method in developing countries. Temporally placed incision has been shown to reduce the occurrence of significant astigmatism due to its lesser effect on the corneal curvature at the visual axis due to neutralization of the drag forces by the eyelid. [9,10] The present study is an observational study to assess the impact of supero temporal Anti Smile (Frown) incision in SICS on the occurrence of post-operative astigmatism.

Materials and Methods

The study was performed in a community-based cataract surgical centre at Government General Hospital, Eluru, located in Andhra Pradesh for the National Blindness Control Program and visual impairment. **Inclusion criteria:** Patients with keratometric astigmatism of less than 1.0 dioptre and good fixation. **Exclusion criteria** Patients with presence of pre-operative astigmatism of more than

1.0 dioptre and traumatic cataract. All individuals with visual impairment due to cataract who fulfilled inclusion criteria were screened between 15-11-2023 to 31-12-2023. All the individuals were screened for hypertension and diabetes mellitus. Patients with pre-existing medical hypertension and diabetes were included in the study after appropriate control of the pre-morbid conditions. Pre operatively keratometry was performed using keratometer. All the surgeries were performed by a single surgeon in a single centre. The incision architecture was similar in all the patients which included a 6-mm superotemporal Anti-Smile Small (Frown) Incision 1.5 mm away from the limbus made with a 2.2 Crescent blade as a funnel shaped sclera-corneal incision. One side port was made at a perpendicular to the main incision and the anterior chamber was entered using a 2.8 mm keratome followed by enlargement of the internal incision sideways up to 6.5 to 7.00 mm to accommodate relatively large nucleus of the mature cataract. Following visco assisted nuclear delivery through the tunnel a three-piece intraocular PMMA Freedom intraocular lens was implanted into the capsular bag. All patients were administered 0.3% Gatifloxacin and 1% prednisolone ocular drops every Three hours every day and tapered off over 4 weeks period. All the patients were followed up for a period of a month. Patients were followed up on 1,7, and 30 post operative days. Keratometric analysis was compared between pre operative and

30 days post operative days. Acceptance of spectacles for best corrected vision with or without cylindrical lens was observed. Amplitude of astigmatism was calculated as the difference between the steeper and flatter meridians in keratometric values using the plus cylindrical notation as described by Holladay et al. [11] Astigmatism was denoted as the magnitude of the value directed towards the steeper meridian.

Results

100 individuals with visual impairment due to cataract were screened between 15-11-2023 to 31-12-2023. A total of 100 individuals with significant visual impairment due to cataract were included in the study. Baseline parameters are shown in Table 1. Females comprised of 54% and males 46% (Figure 1). The mean age of the patients was 59.75 years. Mean preoperative astigmatism was 0.84D. Surgical induced astigmatism of 1 dioptre or more was observed in 7%. Most of the subjects who underwent surgery were observed, and they had no increase in the astigmatism with mean cylindrical axis value of 1.25 Dioptres. There is no statistical significance between genders in the surgically induced astigmatism. Postoperative complications were observed in 18 individuals which were mostly minor. Corneal oedema was observed in 1 individual (0.01%) and striae keratitis in 17 individuals (0.17%) (Figure 6).

Table 1 Baseline characteristics of study subjects (n=100)

Males (n)	46
Females (n)	54
Mean Age	59.73
Mean Age Males	60.02
Mean Age Females	59.48

Figure 1: Distribution of study subjects according to Left Eye and Right Eye

Figure 2: Distribution of study subjects according to Age

Figure 3: Distribution of study subjects according to Gender Ratio

Table 2: Pre OP Best Corrected Visual Acuity

Pre-Operative Best Corrected Visual Acuity			
Visual Acuity	Male	Female	Total
>6/60	15	22	37
6/60 to 3/60	16	11	27
< 3/60	15	21	36
Total	46	54	100

Table 3: Post-operative parameters

Visual Acuity	Immediate Post Op			Final Follow up after a Month		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
6/60 to 6/36	9	10	19	0	0	0
6/24 to 6/18	15	21	36	0	0	0
6/12 to 6/6	22	23	45	46	54	100
Total	46	54	100	46	54	100

Figure 4: Distribution of Study Post Operative Induced Astigmatism among Gender

Figure 5: Distribution of Study Post Operative Induced Astigmatism Among Eye

Figure 6: Post-Operative complications

Discussion

Although phacoemulsification gives excellent results with low incidence of surgically induced astigmatism, [12,13] it is often not feasible in developing countries especially in rural community hospitals in Government sector due to the need for expensive equipment. Suture-less Small Incision Cataract Surgery (SICS) with intraocular lens (IOL) implantation has also shown to give comparable results with low incidence of surgically induced astigmatism. [14] Temporal location of incision for SICS has been shown to have lesser incidence of surgically induced astigmatism with results comparable to phacoemulsification. [15] But beginners it was not an easy to do temporal incision SICS in initial days, In the present study using supero-temporal anti-smile (Frown) incision has shown a low incidence of significant astigmatism of 7 % and the severity of surgical induced astigmatism was low with a mean of 1.25 Dioptres. Similar results have been observed in other studies with SICS [9,15] with economic benefit compared with phacoemulsification. [14,16,17]

Conclusion

Our study has demonstrated that Small Incision Cataract surgery is an effective and safe method in rural community centres. Supero-Temporal Anti-Smile (Frown) incision gives superior results with very low incidence of surgically induced astigmatism with good post operative recovery comparable to superior and straight incision in Small incision Cataract surgery and is ideally suited for community based rural centres where cost and logistics would not permit for expensive phacoemulsification facilities.

Abbreviations

SICS: Small Incision Cataract Surgery. SIA: Surgical Induced Astigmatism.

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References

1. Thulasiraj, RD., Nirmalan, PK., Ramakrishnan, R. *et al.* (2003) Blindness and vision im-

pairment in a rural south Indian population: the Aravind Comprehensive Eye Survey, *Ophthalmology*, 110, pp. 1491–1498.

2. Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, Government of India, New Delhi. (2019) National Blindness & Visual Impairment Survey India 2015-2019- A Summary report. New Delhi: Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, Government of India
3. Chatterjee, A., Milton, R.C., and Thyle, S. (1982) Cataract prevalence and aetiology in Punjab, *British Journal of Ophthalmology*, 66, pp. 35–42.
4. Prajna, NV. *et al.* (1998) The Madurai intraocular lens study II: clinical outcomes, *Am J Ophthalmol*, 125, pp.14–25.
5. Jaffe, N.S. (1976) Cataract surgery and its complications, in St Louis: Mosby. (ed.) pp. 83–98.
6. Gullapalli, V.K., Murthy, P.R., and Murthy, K.R (1995) Colour of the nucleus as a marker of nuclear hardness, diameter and central thickness, *Indian J Ophthalmol*, 43, pp. 181–184.
7. Ayaki, M., Ohde, H., and Yokoyama, N. (1993) Size of the lens nucleus separated by hydrodissection, *Ophthalmic Surg*, 24(7), pp. 492–493.
8. Assia, E.I., Medan, I., and Rosner, M. (1997) Correlation between clinical, physical and histopathological characteristics of the cataractous lens, *Graefes Arch Clin Exp Ophthalmol*, 235(12), pp. 745–748.
9. Gokhale, N.S., Sawhney, S. (2005) Reduction in Astigmatism in Small Incision Cataract Surgery through change of incision site, *Indian J Ophthalmol*, 53, pp. 201–203.
10. Merriam, J.C., Zheng, L., Urbanowicz, J., and Zaider, M. (2001) Change on the horizontal and vertical meridians of the cornea after cataract surgery, *Trans Am Ophthalmol Soc*, 99, pp. 187–95.
11. Holladay, J.T., Dudeja, T.R., and Koch, D.D. (1998) Evaluating and reporting astigmatism for individual and aggregate data, *J Cataract Refract Surg*, 24, pp. 57–65.
12. Yoon, Y-C., Ha, M., Whang, W-J. (2021) Comparison of surgically induced astigmatism between anterior and total cornea in 2.2 mm steep meridian incision cataract surgery, *BMC Ophthalmol*, 21, pp. 373.
13. George, R., Rupauliha, P., Sripriya, A.V. *et al.* (2005) 'Comparison of Endothelial Cell Loss and Surgically Induced Astigmatism following Conventional Extra Capsular Cataract extraction, Small-incision Surgery and Phacoemulsification, *Ophthalmic Epidemiology*, 12, pp. 293–297.
14. Gogate, P., Deshpande, M., and Nirmalan, P.K. (2007) Why do phacoemulsification?

- small- incision cataract surgery is almost as effective, but less expensive, *Ophthalmology*, 114(5), pp. 965-8.
15. Reddy, B., Raj, A., Singh, V.P. (2007) Site of Incision and Corneal Astigmatism in Conventional SICS and Phacoemulsification, *Annals of Ophthalmol*, 39(3), pp. 209.
 16. Muralikrishnan, R., Venkatesh, R., Prajna, N.V., and Frick, K.D. (2004) 'Economic cost of cataract surgery procedures in an established eye care centre in Southern India, *Ophthalmic Epidemiol*, 11, pp. 369–80.
 17. Pawar, V.S., Sindal, D.K. (2012) A Comparative study on Superior, Supero-Temporal and Temporal Incisions in Small Incision Cataract Surgeries for Post Operative Astigmatism, *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research*, 6(7), pp. 1229-1232.